

METHODOLOGY AND PROGRAMMING TASKS OF RURAL DEVELOPMENT MANAGEMENT

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Abstract— The paper analyzes the goals and objectives of socio-economic development of the regions at the current stage of economic development of Uzbekistan. It also proposes criteria for assessing the development of rural territorial systems, the principles of their management and the main conditions.

Keywords—rural territorial systems, socio-economic development, management, criteria, welfare program, rural population.

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

If the most important condition for the development of market relations in the economy in accordance with world standards is the formation of multi-sectoral structures in rural areas, the formation of governance structures, the formation of management systems and expanding access to economic methods of management. The current management policy is aimed at further development of the agricultural sector of the economy, the export of the interests and needs of the local population. The development of processing enterprises, transport preparation networks and storage facilities is one of the important tasks of the current stage. All this is necessary to eliminate the imbalances between the sectors of the agro-industrial complex (AIC), prioritize the development of agricultural sectors and, as a result, strengthen the socio-economic situation in rural areas, increase the level of food and social services increase.

In such circumstances, it is important to increase the export potential of products, eliminate the imbalance between production and consumption, as well as to improve the structure of agro-industrial production, which will improve the social situation of the rural population.

One of the effective tools for studying these processes is modeling. Naturally, the implementation of such tasks requires the development of ways to manage the processes of socio-economic development of the regions. In this regard, the

study of socio-economic development of small and medium-sized rural areas on the basis of modeling the system of territorial governance and forecasting determines the relevance of the research topic.

With this in mind, it is necessary to develop methods for forecasting and managing the processes of economic and social development of rural territorial systems and test them on the example of small and medium rural areas.

The subject of the research is focused on the processes of forecasting the management and development of the socio-economic system of rural areas. Socio-economic indicators of Khojayli district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan as an object of research selected.

II. RESEARCH METODOLOGY

Development of a program to further improve the welfare of the rural population and substantiation of the criteria for managing the socio-economic development of the region forms the basis.

In this regard, it is necessary to develop ways and means to ensure a qualitatively new level of well-being of the population. First of all, it is necessary to know the ways to ensure the growth trends of the population, to determine the population's food supply and demand for non-food products. These circumstances provide an opportunity to form a program of socio-economic development of the region. With this in mind, it is necessary to develop criteria for assessing the development of the area where the program is being developed. There are different views on the criteria for assessing the socio-economic development of the region. He suggested an indicator of the level of "demand and consumption" as a criterion for assessing the socio-economic development of the region. Territorial development in some studies the criterion of "population quality" is proposed. It involves the calculation of the coefficient of quality of the population. The quality indicator of the population is calculated in the form of the ratio of the number of physiologically defective population in natural growth to the number of population growth in the current year is calculated in terms of the ratio of the number of physiologically defective populations.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Researches of foreign and domestic scientists are devoted to problems of management of processes of social and economic development of regional systems. In the work of Russian researchers Krutikov V.K, Zaytsev Yu.V., Dorojkina T.V, Kostina O.I, Fedorova O.V elements of the regional socio-economic system, features, program-targeted methods of territorial administration, foreign policy of regional administration and social

psychological aspects, including local practices, modern governance innovations, have been studied [2]. Pogonin A.V.'s article identifies key factors in the development of the Molda region, taking into account the key role of cities and clusters. It considered issues related to determining the position of cities in the hierarchy of regions. An authoring model of the cluster has been proposed [3]. Classification of socio-economic processes in the article of Kondratev D.A. identified. The concept and essence of socio-economic development of the formation of a rural municipality is revealed [4]. Nikolaev M.A., Maxotaeva M.Yu. His research focuses on regional economics and management. In particular, the authors present the basic theoretical approaches to the study of the conceptual apparatus, as well as processes in different levels of territorial systems [5].

The written monograph, edited by Professor M.Yu. Sheresheva, explores the theoretical aspects of the study of the interaction of municipalities in the network, and describes the practical methods and approaches to its modeling [6]. Anishchenko M.A., Volivak O.K. and other authors [7] in their monographs on theoretical approaches and concepts in specific areas of science and education, analytical commentary. listed. Asadov H.S., an uzbek researcher, discusses the dynamics of economic growth in the regions, their stratification, changes in the sectoral structure of regional economic production and the existing imbalances. [8]. In addition, [9] in the study, the goals and objectives of the management of socio-economic processes, in which the indicator of the level of "demand and consumption" is proposed as the main criterion. [10], in his scientific work, suggested that the natural environment and production, the preservation of simple wealth, the development of the region "as a criterion for assessing the quality of the population.

IV. METHODOLOGY AND PROGRAMMING TASKS

From a methodological point of view, at the current stage it is necessary to pay special attention to the requirements for the construction of the management system of the agro-industrial complex. A three-step approach to modeling socio-economic development management in rural areas has also been proposed. At the same time, it is necessary to create ways to digitize models of management of socio-economic development of rural areas.

The problem of social development of the village is the largest in the republic and has a political, social and economic nature. This problem is especially acute in the context of the constant growth of the rural population. Today, rural society is far behind the city in terms of social development, and the conclusion is that it is necessary to find effective ways and means to radically improve the

living standards of the single population. But this is just a village wax to solve the problems of raising the economy of the farm.

The main indicators of material well-being are relatively low, especially in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, which we are studying. Agriculture and industrial goods food prices products noticeable from the norms in the village. The consumption of basic foodstuffs lags far behind natural norms.

These are indicators of the level of development of the industry is far below rational norms. Village children require coverage with preschools, the network of schools is also underdeveloped. Cultural institutions There are many flaws in the system. Schools of information and communication The starting point of equipping with networks is now increasing. In short, all of these are basic material and social needs which does not prescribe a minimum allowable landing low social conditions for the rural population, allows us to conclude that. In this regard, the rural population is shady-economic blindly to the need to improve living conditions processing is required. Organizational development and rural welfare management there was a need to develop a targeted program. This is it term of the program the ultimate goal is the morality of the content of social policy began to meet the goals of forming a materially rich person, consumption of social and cultural benefits neutral ensuring a qualitatively new level of well-being. The most important directions and tools are the calculation of the seed material, aimed at the formation of a rich person, and cultural blessings Develop the most important directions and tools that will bring the welfare of social consumption to a qualitatively new level colic.

The target of such a program is each for the department should be able to carry out developments with an analytical description of the forecast, which is distributed over the years. This will allow the target program to be integrated with the Socio-Economic Development Plan of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main directions of the development of the socio-economic program of the regions are as follows;

- First of all, the assessment of current trends in the demographic situation, the age at which the forecasting of the population, labor force and age structure is carried out reproduction. On this basis it is necessary to identify the most important areas of demographic policy in relation to the demographic situation in the region and the employment of labor resources in the region in general.
- The most important indicator of the living standards of the population is the per capita consumption of food and other goods. Therefore, forecasting the demand of the population for food products by their prices is, first of all, the necessary level of income of the population. Secondly, it allows to determine the

production volumes allocated for the consumption of rural and urban population. There should be a special section in the program to forecast food supply, taking into account the growth of the population, the need for per capita production. In this regard, the forecast for the development of agriculture in the private and private sectors is envisaged. This should take into account the environmental situation in agriculture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the limited resources of land, water and labor, the introduction of technology, the specialization of farms and a number of other socio-economic factors. farmer specialization and a number of other socio-economic factors must be taken into account.

- The program should pay special attention to the development of social infrastructure in rural areas. Taking into account population growth, it is necessary to forecast the needs of the village in housing, health care facilities, kindergartens and preschools. All this makes it possible to designate the relevant sections of the rural social reconstruction program. and the goals of achieving it.

- The social development of the countryside cannot be considered in isolation from the economic conditions of the functioning and development of agriculture and other branches of material production. Socio-economic goal setting, following the process of making sound management decisions development programs allows you to go and make some adjustments to the programs in a timely manner if necessary. All this prevents the possibility of subjectivity in the management and planning of improving the living standards of the population. In this regard, it is necessary to develop criteria for assessing the socio-economic development of the regions where the programs are being developed.

There are different views in the literature on the criteria for assessing the level of socio-economic development of the region. An indicator of "demand and consumption" has been proposed in the study as a criterion for assessing socio-economic development [2-9]. From this point of view, the authors of this study showed the acceptance of living standards as a criterion for the effectiveness of a particular region (district) and the programs and solutions being developed.

In view of this, it is proposed to consider the preservation of the natural environment and the level of production of material wealth as a criterion for assessing the "population quality" of the development of the region. We propose to calculate the quality coefficient (Kq) of the population formed in this area according to the following formula:

$$K_q = 1 - \frac{N_d}{N}$$

where, N - is the natural increase in population in the current year; N_d - is the number of physiologically and other defective populations in natural growth. If population growth is increasing, $K_q(t) \rightarrow 1$, then the average coefficient of reproductive intelligence can be used to measure the quality level of the population:

$$J_{aver}(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum J_j(t)$$

where, $J_j(t)$ - j - is the coefficient of reproductive intelligence of the population of the sex group. The dynamics of change in the quality coefficient of the population over time shows the direction of development of this increase and allows to analyze the causes in a timely manner and make the necessary decisions, that is, to manage population growth. The essence of the proposed criterion is revealed in the model of global development: the population and its quality must be maintained in such a way that the production of the necessary material goods does not lead to a deterioration of the natural living environment of people. To implement such a model, the authors proposed the creation of three systems of global monitoring - population, natural (environmental, weather, etc.), production systems. An integral part of such systems should be local or regional systems, as these systems are interrelated with commodity exchange and reproduction. From this, a model of local (territorial) development is built. Its basic premise is to "preserve the natural environment and ensure the quality of life needed in this area".

All of these theoretical considerations [2-9,10] are in principle consistent with the requirements of human development and economic growth. The difficulty arises in something else. How can these theoretical propositions be put into practice? Naturally, calculation paths should be developed based on a system of indicators based on a system of indicators that provide access to managed and controlled socio-economic data that affects quality of life and economic growth. Socio-economic in this regard an attempt was made to combine elements of regional systems to develop models of development processes. Therefore, the existing areas are divided into large, medium and small rural areas. Large areas are the territories of regions or regions (2-3 regions), the average areas are administrative districts and micro-zones. Small rural areas regardless of this form of ownership, one or two different types of production of agro-industrial complex or other industries are concentrated. the territories of the three farms. In some cases, small rural areas are compatible with rural council areas. To

manage the socio-economic development of territorial systems, the author developed a schematic diagram of the interrelationships between the elements of the natural environment, production and population (Figure 1). It is known that in any region there are three interconnected systems: nature, population, production systems. Population is a part of nature, characterized by elements of nature, and the producer of products is at the same time the consumer of products.

Fig. 1. Socio-economic status of territorial systems development control chart.

In 2020, the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan will be 34.6 million people, of which 17.5 million (50.6%) are urban and 17.4 million are rural. From 2020, the urban-rural ratio has stabilized (50:50). Although their absolute growth is observed. The urban population will increase by 1.9 million by 2020 compared to 1991, while the rural population will increase by 3.1 million during this period multiplied by man.

According to the average life expectancy in Uzbekistan (Table 1), in 2010 it was 73.0 years, in 2019 - 75.1 years, including 70.1 years for men and 75.1 years for women. that is, 5.9 and 8.1 years of age respectively. Life expectancy in the United States and life expectancy in France is 6.4 and 9.2 years, respectively. These data suggest that in the near future the quantitative growth of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan should be accompanied by "qualitative" growth. To do this, it is necessary to create systems for studying and managing demographic processes in the regions. This system measures population (B), their age (B2), gender composition (vz), and more. They allow the population to forecast their needs for labor resources, food, housing, goods and services, as well as their income and expenses. A characteristic feature of Uzbekistan's nature is its warm climate, which also provides access to irrigation. However, many crops are considered heat-loving. Therefore, the three factors of agricultural development depend on the availability of irrigated land (A1), water resources (A2), and the length of the growing season (A3).

The land area of the Republic of Uzbekistan is 44.8 million hectares. Of these, 20.2 million hectares are used by agricultural enterprises. Consumption of clean water in the republic 52.4 cu. km, of which 44.4 cubic meters. km was used for irrigation and water supply of agriculture.

Irrigated lands are the most valuable, accounting for 4.3 million hectares or 9.5% of the total land area of the Republic of Uzbekistan, of which 3.9 million hectares are arable land.

Life expectancy in Uzbekistan

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2018
Total	73.0	73.0	73.1	73.1	73.1	73.6	73.8	73.7	71.6	75.1
Women	75.1	75.2	75.5	75.8	75.8	76.0	76.2	76.1	77.0	77.4
Men	70.6	70.5	70.7	71.1	71.1	71.2	71.4	71.3	72.3	72.8
City population	73.1	73.2	73.2	73.6	73.5	74.0	74.5	74.4	75.4	75.8
Women	75.7	75.9	76.0	76.0	76.2	76.8	77.1	77.1	78.0	78.3
Men	70.4	70.5	70.4	71.0	70.8	71.3	71.8	71.7	72.6	73.2
Rural population	72.7	72.5	72.8	73.1	73.2	73.0	73.0	72.8	73.8	74.2
Women	74.5	74.3	74.7	75.1	75.2	75.0	74.9	74.8	75.7	76.2
Men	71.0	70.8	71.0	71.3	71.3	71.0	71.1	71.0	71.9	72.4

As noted above, the further development of agriculture and, consequently, the provision of food to the population, the material and social condition depends on the condition and volume of land and water resources. Therefore, they must be suitable for the normal life and human activities of the people living in this area. Human impact on the natural environment should not exceed its potential, in particular, rural areas should be covered by industrial enterprises, unorganized agriculture, population migration, depletion of water resources and so on.

In order to ensure the sustainable development of territories, human activity must show such a load on the natural environment that society does not go beyond the boundaries of the use of the natural environment. All of this requires finding optimal ways to use natural resources in a way that will ensure that future generations do not waste their valuable resources on future generations. To do this, it is necessary to monitor the condition of irrigated lands (measure the level of groundwater, humus reserves in the soil), regulate wastewater and control the irrigation regime, and create systems for measuring FAR. helps to increase.

The national income generated in the country in 2019 amounted to 355531.3 billion. or 10,385.9 thousand sums of income per capita. 74% of the national income is spent on consumption, 26% - on savings and other expenses. 45% of

the population's income came from personal subsidiary plots, stipends, pensions, and other incomes from the consumer fund accounted for 15.8%.

The level of production and income per capita in the country is still low, which has a significant impact on the well-being of the population. The primary task is to find the most rational production facilities that provide the population of the republic not only with food and clothing, but also with real income. Therefore, it is necessary to move to the optimal structure of agro-industrial production with the organization of deep processing and production of ready-to-eat products in the conditions of stabilization of cotton fiber production to 1.5 million tons. This, in turn, solves the problem of employment of the rural population and family income. Hence, the system of production and consumption should include the production of final products per capita (C1), the measurement and management of land (C2), material resources (C3), as well as the income of the population and families (C4) and should be managed.

Thus, in the nature-population-production system, the state of the natural environment, the level of production of material goods, a set of factors that reflect the income and expenditure of the population are managed. Analysis, forecasting of these factors, socio-economic development and management include the performance of various tasks for the purpose of shaping the programs of territorial systems.

Conclusion

Socio-economic development of agriculture in small and medium-sized areas is the basis of the current reforms in Uzbekistan. Strategically, this will be an important basis for employment and sustainable livelihoods.

In order to assess the socio-economic development of rural areas and its +2 results, this study is based on the criterion of "population quality". Its essence includes such concepts as ensuring the health, well-being and prosperity of the population of the region inside.

A model of systematic management of socio-economic development and a target program for its implementation are proposed, taking into account the criteria based on the study and the indicators that reveal its essence.

The future development of rural areas depends on the balance of natural resources, the demographic situation of the population, the supply and demand for production and consumption. With this in mind, there is ample opportunity for demographic growth, an increase in the labor force and an increase in incomes in the regions of the country. and this population.

Further development of the agrarian structure of the new Uzbekistan requires the effective use of factors of nature, population, production, and this

requires the introduction of domestic and foreign investment in new areas of development.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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